

Application of Smart Pixels to Digital Image Halftoning

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Abstract

An innovative circuit for digital image halftoning applications has been implemented in several different hybrid fabrication processes. The circuits have been demonstrated to be compatible with several approaches to smart pixels and offer a wide range of options for realizing optical inputs and outputs. The 0.8 micron n-well CMOS process at MOSIS has been used in conjunction with SEED technology to implement a digital image halftoning algorithm that offers the potential for higher quality binary images. Similar algorithms have also been implemented using combined CMOS and liquid crystal on silicon processes as well as the Vitesse H-GaAs III foundry process.

1. Introduction

The growing interest in optoelectronic devices over the past five to ten years has led to a shift in emphasis from all-optical systems to hybrid optoelectronic architectures based on technologies such as smart pixel arrays. Optoelectronic circuits show promise as a means of improving performance of military computing and signal processing applications that are subject to the input/output and interconnection limitations characteristic of large scale digital switching and communications systems. We have designed and fabricated several smart pixel integrated circuits to demonstrate new signal and image processing architectures developed over the past four years. The first circuit combines the speed of optics with the versatility of silicon very large scale integrated (VLSI) circuit technology to implement an optical analog-to-digital (A/D) conversion circuit. A second integrated circuit implements an error diffusion neural network approach to digital image halftoning. This error diffusion algorithm has also been implemented in processes such as liquid crystal on silicon [1,2] (LCOS) and high-performance GaAs. This paper describes how optical inputs/outputs have been combined with analog

and digital circuitry in a smart pixel configuration to achieve the desired functionality.

2. Optical A/D Conversion

The portion of the integrated circuit chip shown in Figure 1 is the first hardware implementation of a novel approach to optoelectronic A/D conversion based on oversampling and error diffusion coding.

Figure 1. Section of smart pixel integrated circuit chip showing error diffusion modulator.

Oversampled A/D conversion is based on a one-dimensional, temporal form of error diffusion coding, whereby a large error associated with a single sample is diffused over many subsequent samples. The error to be diffused is generated by a low resolution quantizer which is normally embedded in a feedback architecture along with a linear filter. The analog signal is sampled at a rate much greater than the Nyquist rate and fed into a modulator which provides coarse amplitude quantization and spectral shaping of the quantization noise. A postprocessor then removes the quantization noise and reduces the signal sampling rate to the Nyquist rate. The error diffusion modulator shown in the block diagram in Figure 2 has been implemented in 2.0 micron CMOS using a selection of digital and analog circuits. The optical input to the modulator is detected by a silicon phototransistor that generates the corresponding current in a series of MOSFETs configured as current mirrors. Signal processing is accomplished with current addition, subtraction, and multiplication throughout the circuit.

Figure 2. Block diagram of error diffusion modulator.

As shown by the schematic in Figure 3, the input to the comparator is determined by the difference between the input photocurrent and the error current. In this implementation of Figure 2, the comparator serves as the quantizer or thresholding circuit for the modulator. A

Figure 3. Circuit implementation of a one-bit error diffusion modulator.

delay from an externally controlled latch circuit has been inserted into the feedback loop to allow single bit operation. The output of the comparator goes through the delay circuit and then selects either a positive or negative current that, when added to the current from the feed-forward circuit, creates the error current. Having an output in the form of a one-bit digital word, the comparator also drives an amplifier that modulates a resonant cavity enhanced (RCE) LED [3] which provides the optical output signal. These emitter circuits are bonded directly to the silicon chip using epitaxial lift-off and bump bonding [4]. On-chip silicon drivers provide the bias current for the RCE LEDs.

3. Digital Image Halftoning

An investigation of the single-bit modulator led to the development of a novel technique for digital image halftoning using an error diffusion neural network. When applied in a two-dimensional array, the modulator circuit can become a digital image halftoning algorithm if the error signal from each pixel is fed to all other pixels, but not to itself. Since real-time processing occurs and the error is diffused away from each pixel, a delay circuit is not required. The integrated circuit in Figure 4 is a 0.8 micron CMOS implementation of a 5x5 array of modulators. Each of the 25 cells is a smart pixel

Figure 4. Digital image halftoning neural network chip.

composed of a signal processing neuron and weighting and feedback interconnect circuitry as shown in Figure 5. Neuron circuitry at the top of this figure is similar to the input and quantizer implementation in Figure 3, except the thresholding is accomplished by a transconductance amplifier biased near or below threshold [5] instead of a simple comparator. Approximately 75% of the neuron is dedicated to weighting of the error current and feeding the correct percentage to other nodes in the network. Each weighted error must be capable of being represented by either a positive or negative current, depending upon whether the quantizer output is greater than or less than the input. Every cell is custom designed for a particular position in the network such that the error current is properly distributed to nearest neighbors. The central smart pixel is the most complex, with

Figure 5. Central smart pixel neuron of a 5x5 array.

approximately 90 transistors required to implement the complex error diffusion pattern shown in Figure 6. The neural network is designed to compute quantization decisions in parallel and, with proper distribution of error, improve the quality of halftoned images.

Optical inputs and outputs are via a 10 x 20 array of multiple quantum-well self-electro-optic-effect devices (SEEDs) flip-chip bonded to the silicon chip [6] at the

Figure 6. Error diffusion pattern for center pixel of a 5x5 array of neurons.

third metal level. The pitch of the array is 250 microns. When reversed biased, a SEED can be used as a photoreceiver. For this application, these devices are adequate for detecting the optical input. When reversed biased to an adequate level, a SEED will emit light that is capable of being detected by a CCD camera.

4. Other Implementations

A similar error diffusion algorithm has been implemented with a 3x3 array of error diffusion modulators fabricated in 2.0 micron CMOS and liquid crystal on silicon. The single pixel in Figure 7 shows a

Figure 7. One pixel of CMOS/LCOS implementation of an error diffusion modulator.

pn junction photodiode on the left side to detect the optical input and a metal2 pad on the right to modulate the liquid crystal region. As in previous implementations, the input photocurrent is combined with the error current to create the drive voltage for the transconduction amplifier. At the output, a simple inverter controls the voltage on the metal pad which sets the polarization of the liquid crystal material above it. For each pixel of the 3x3 array, the reflection/absorption of incident polarized light is determined by the field applied to the liquid crystal via the metal pad and the output of the transconductance amplifier or quantizer.

One additional implementation of the error diffusion algorithm has been completed. Using the Vitesse H-GaAs III process [7], a 3x3 array of smart pixels has been designed around a MESFET quantizer, buffered optical MESFET inputs, and 880 nm LED outputs.

5. Conclusion

Four different technologies have been used to implement an error diffusion algorithm that promises improved image quality in digital halftoning processes. Design of optical inputs and outputs has taken advantage of emerging technologies such as resonant cavity enhanced LEDs, self electro-optic effect devices, liquid crystal on silicon, and GaAs emitters. These different processes will be compared as alternatives for smart pixel applications such as digital image halftoning.

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